

Research article

The importance of leadership training for Head of Department: a study of a public university in Afghanistan

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Accepted: 12 April, 2020; Online: 19 April, 2020

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3756270>

Abstract: This little research has adapted clearly on the system of identifying comprehensive training prerequisites for HOD and shows the designed plan and activity of a program to generally consider the activity requirements for HOD of universities. Results from a couple of step plans opened those reports and supporting, personnel matters, legitimate issues, expert improvement of HOD. Managers had positioned as the most important preparation required. Benefits of these strategy techniques will reduce issues to get achievement, potential cut off points, ways for up and coming examination, are pondered.

Keywords: Head of department, Leadership, Trainings, management, public university

Introduction

There are different clarifications of leadership as everywhere are the leader. All leaders have a select attractive plan, impacted by character, and the difficulties met in the authority character. Anyway styles of the administration continue unique, here are capabilities that every excessive leadership shares. These comprise of Accountability, Awareness, Confidence, Decisiveness, Empathy, Focus, Honesty, Inspiration, and Optimism. M. L. (2018) said that a developing variety of research recommends that leaders are vital to supporting innovation because by showing positive, strong administration practices, they urge followers to take a stab at being frequently innovative. People look to leaders to advise them about their exercises. Nice leaders are saint models for the people they lead, moving them, helping them and supporting correspondences among them. In the business, great authority means long haul accomplishment

with high certainty and a high level of worker holding. Publics require rules and laws to deal with their exercises. Associations of any size explanation of the characters of their leaders. A decent initiative advantage figure an inspirational mentality supports concordance and encourages incomparable profit. Leadership preparation is a program that must-go-to for all associations and all directorial leaders. The constrained research that has tried this relationship is centered on the openness business, and the experimental proof is as yet deficient (Chang and Teng 2017). We subsequently propose and test the thought that when individuals can produce new, valuable thoughts, they accomplish better work execution, with the end goal that worker's inventiveness should positively affect works effecting. Doing it precisely expects regard for the fundamental abilities that help leaders affect others. Later completing this structure, you'll have a release, research, and assets for the corporate learning and supper leader. The term head of the Department relates to chosen post holders who have an obligation for either an academic department. Heads of Department are chosen by and are responsible to the Pro-Vice-Chancellor Faculty. Without a doubt, Smith (2002), in an investigation portraying HOD at British colleges, noticed that there is minimal exact research on the board in advanced education. The absence of preparation and a corresponding deficiency of research on the best way to recognize, encounter the preparation requirements of chairs to complete this basic jobs are together significant apprehensions.

The main role of the Head of a Department is to produce reliable academic leadership. All HOD's are necessary to practice power, make a dream, and employ others to fulfill the recognized departmental form and procedure inside the personnel. Using leadership and management skills of department heads direct and encourage employees in a department. They might adjust work activities and employ for fresh staff, among other responsibilities. Functioning with other leaders and officials, they control the yearly financial goals of the department and confirm departmental achievement. All HOD's are required to practice authority, show vision, and enable others to carry the approved departmental policy inside the Faculty.

The leadership is a title that has created different ideas for a significant length of time, it depicts and ground-breaking commanders that have vanquished domains, CEOs who composed and coordinated corporate associations; government officials who formed the course of their countries, strict people who affected their devotees, and activists who enlivened their

extraordinary supporters D. A. (2017). It is perceived that the techniques, by which HOD complete their duties and the degree of responsibility. This will rely upon such issues as the size and condition of the Departments and the individual methodology of the individual HOD.

In Afghanistan, higher education is providing by public and private higher education institutions. Afghanistan now has 39 public and more than 128 private higher education institutions. MoHE (2017) stated that as a result of delightful growth seen in private higher education institutions, the MoHE is presently resulting and policy hesitant the formation of private universities. The education curriculum is drawn up by the MoHE. Universities generally only offer bachelor's and master's degree programs. Afghanistan has hardly been able to develop master's programs due to countless wars. Under the National Higher Education Strategic Plan (NHEP), Afghanistan has scheduled to establish a variety of master's (MA) degree programs indoors a few years. Master's degree programs presently are in teaching and engineering. M. (2009), stated that in the previous year few private universities also launched master's degree programs. These were primarily established in link with international universities from various countries, such as Sweden, Germany, the USA, and the United Kingdom. For getting admission in higher education, students are compulsory to pass the Kankuor examination after having achieved the 12 Grade Certificate. If they pass the examination, students can get admission to a selected degree program, dependent on their marks and personal interests. The entry test is structured once a year. If students fail the examination, they are essential to sit next year in examination.

Literature review

Abundant of the literature portraying the HOD has mindful of employments done by the HOD; vulnerability in the worldwide market has made associations increasingly mindful and inclined to receive change on a persistent premise. The unpredictability of the business activities requires that there must be powerful cooperation from each degree of the association K. P. (2016). Andersen (2016) expressed that leaders are the ones who animate, inspire, and perceive their representatives to complete work and accomplish the ideal outcomes. Pioneers embrace different administration styles to inspire and invigorate representatives.

The objective of this exploration is to examine how group execution is impacted by leadership styles in the open part, going up against the points of view of the leaders with the impression of their groups, R. S. G. E. (2017). Directing electrophysiological chronicles in the mix with coulometer conduct requires a strategy for keeping up the obsession with the head and a good technique permitting ceaseless access to the cerebrum Everling, S. (2018). Working memory (Collins et al. 1998; Spinelli et al. 2004; Takemoto et al. 2011; Yamazaki et al. 2016), along these lines permitting the chance of consolidating hereditary and social neuroscience, approaches in primate animal groups. Arif (2016) considers the executives and gaps in the leadership in a college to comprehend its change and quality improvement. He utilizes a fundamental examination to propose the best hierarchical improvement for the college.

Arif (2016) notices that most organizations think that administration improvement and change management are discrete. Truth be told, they are interrelated. For instance, social changes can't happen without powerful administration, and efforts to change culture are the reason for administration. Galli et al. (2016) noted there are paths to address and prevent issues in organizations. Here and there, the most testing part is understanding the issue(s). Goodwin (2016) examines the change in the management practice of First Manufacturing Cost Global (FMCG). He studies the differences found in performance, regardless of whether they face related leadership issues to different clients when realizing showing devices, for example, Six Sigma, how their leadership course was organized, and the greatest restrictions affecting change administration. Studies confirm that 50-70% of all arranged change falls flat (Galli et al., 2016). Many organizations win out in operational and supporting change, yet not in change relating to the people. The recommended approach to achieve total change is through Change Leadership and Management. Leadership allows a vital job in making an exciting climate and culture in an association (Alghazo and Al-Anazi, 2016). Dallyay and Jalagat (2016) directed research on title Impacts of Leadership Style adequacy of Managers and Department Heads to Employees' Job Satisfaction and Performance. V and Z. (2017). Given the outcomes, the fair leadership style has a hugely positive effect on employee's implementation. This demonstrates when the popularity based methodology is applied, the show of representatives would increment. Along these lines, Malaysian leaders are urged to embrace a popularity based leadership style and include colleagues in the dynamic procedure since it is affirmed that the presence of workers is the best

under this style of leadership. The social procedure of sense-production happens at both administrative and group levels (Laine, Korhonen, and Martinsuo, 2016).

All in all, the exploration discoveries of Packard and Kauppi (1999), Yahya and Ebrahim (2016) and Spano Szekely (2016) showed that distinctive leadership styles, when embraced by leaders bring about various degrees of employment fulfillment. For example, leaders' help and acknowledgment bring a more elevated level of occupation fulfillment among workers. The process toward a perception of the key jobs of the head of the department is a proper source of evaluation of the special knowledge, skills, and abilities.

Method

This qualitative study was conducted with semi-structured interviews with the head of the department in a public university in Afghanistan. It looks at how the head of the department perceives the role of the head of department. All over, the Afghan research into the role of these entities performances as a standard to match the condition in Afghan public universities. Of course, we have to take great care not to assume that what is optimum for a university in Afghanistan. Nevertheless, there may still be lessons to be learned concerning maximizing the value of those individuals who act as middle-level leaders in such universities.

The main objective of the research was to explore perceptions of the role of the head of the department in public universities in Afghanistan. This was done by trying to answer the following research questions:

1. Do they receive any preparation courses or programs before officially appointed as organizational/school leaders?
2. How did they perceive the preparation program or courses that they were attended?
3. What are the benefits that they obtained after completing the relevant preparation courses or programs relevant to their roles as school/organizational leaders?
4. What are other relevant preparation/continuation courses that insisted by organizational/school leaders that insisted to assist them to become effective school/organizational leaders?

To answer these questions, data was obtained by using semi-structured interviews.

Participant

The foremost participant was the head of the department of a public university in Afghanistan with a strong corporate experience, a strong global behavior, and an effective academic resume. The complete interview was taken in the office of the respective interviewees. The interview released to share their understanding regarding leadership, training and its value is as the head of the department.

The interviewee was the head of the department of a public university in Afghanistan with stable corporate support, a solid worldwide nearness, and a great academic resume. The whole meeting was taken in the workplace separately. The meeting authorized people to share their perception in regards to authority, preparing and its worth is as head of the department.

Data Collection

An interview convention was set up to coordinate the research objectives and research questions this study. The interview questions were semi-organized to permit different inquiries to develop during the interviewing procedure and extra thoughts could be investigated. The utilization of the meeting guide permitted more structure, which thusly facilitated the researcher's undertaking of arranging and breaking down interview information. The general air in all interviews was exceptionally easygoing, with the interviewees giving complete consideration around then. Although their capacity to focus, their relational abilities and their capacity for self-reflection contributed significantly to the nature of the meetings. Each interview directed took around 45 minutes. A recorder gadget was utilized with consent from those met.

An interview was supported with an analysis of archives containing a speech and an open talk on subjects of pre and post-preparing of the head of department. The discourses were additionally recorded with authorization from the head of department. Field notes with depictions, direct citations, and onlooker remarks were recorded not long after the perceptions (Merriam, 1998). For that reason, the analyst hauled around her diary and recorded her perceptions at the earliest opportunity after a perception.

Data Analysis

This interview was semi-structured and sound recorded, recorded accurately and one member was the head of department of a public university in Afghanistan. An outline was sent to the participants for respondent confirmation, the member checked this rundown. The Analysis began straightforwardly after the meeting and proceeded at the same time with information collection. The subjects picked for our meetings dependent on the unique authority preparing when special leadership training for before and after appointing of head of department, whereby the ideas of occupation assets, work requests, and job communication were at first viewed as primary topics. Related watchwords for an asset could show positive feelings or articulations, related catchwords for request could demonstrate negative feelings or articulations. We likewise made notes if such remarks were made according to one job or if these influenced different jobs. One citation could contain different codes. During the examination, codes and results were talked about among different creators consistently to additionally refine coding and think about rising topics. We again surveyed our codes utilizing work commitment writing and chose to include as sharpening ideas execution input and assets and requests on an individual level as a sharpening idea. All the more explicitly, we remembered for the layout whether an asset or request was owing to the work or the member, utilizing indistinguishable watchwords from previously. Now, the codes stayed unaltered yet an elective course of action of subjects was picked to wager after every update of the topics and codes, all past interview was returned to and broke down with the new coding structure.

Identified themes

Interviewers should build up a positive early introduction. They should dress expertly men in ties even on 1st April, 2020, albeit marginally increasingly easygoing clothing is best when the respondents are monetarily burdened. Expressing gratitude toward the respondent for the gathering and offering a business card can add to proficient validity.

To keep the voice record or not, that is a key informed decision. A little advanced device, if authorization is in all actuality, permits the questioner to be all the more effectively occupied with the discussion just as to consider the best next inquiry as opposed to focusing on recording answers. Be that as it may if the points secured area at all delicate, respondents might be

repressed by an account gadget, regardless of whether complete privacy whenever guaranteed and assent is given; a few people overlook the recorder is running, however, others remain watchful.

When taking notes, questioners ought to do as well as can be expected by personal frameworks. We must utilize quotes once composing exact expressions. Numerous minutes reworded and ought to be preserved as after composing the facts; however, it is essential to record in exactly the same words and put quotes around an especially significant or paramount remark.

Special program and trainings

The data obtained from the respondent about providing a special training for appoint a head of department. It is indicated that:

“There are no special program and training to be held for HOD before or after pointing him/her that whenever an employee is designated in the relevant department of organization, there are particular job requirements and specifications and he/she is selected through a voting system of relevant staff of the department.”

. (F. W. 1999) stated that the skills needed to be an effective department chair differ greatly from those required to be a successful faculty member. To make the transition from professor to administrator and professor, beginning chairs must learn to master a complex array of new, unfamiliar tasks.

Refection of Program

In every education directorate there is not any type of preparation course, workshop or seminar held by the HOD. Almost in every educational organization has not had to get preparation course or workshops that attended before the appointing as head of department:

“I did not received any kind of preparation program when I was appointing as head of department, So, this is what I said to the to, The very first thing I want to tell you that when I appointed, I did not know any things about head of department and how to operate the department (April 1)”

So, it is cleared that the government has not any special program or training courses before the appointment but has workshops and seminars but after the appointing there are several short terms programs provided by related ministries. Wolverton et al. (1 999b) proposed that the impacts of such pressure might be enhanced, in any event somewhat, through different kinds of trainings. Generally speaking, a successful preparation platform is expected to recover acts and success although, lessening pressure and takings.

Leadership Quality

The data gained from the respondent about relevant leadership courses and programs which you attended and how are you using as head of department:

“There we do not have any criteria or special course as like in Malaysia or other countries held by the government and after passing the mention special course, someone will be able to work as a leader or in leadership authority. Unfortunate I do not attend any preparation course in our country after appointing as a leader”

The special courses and trainings have a vital role in leadership and as a head of department. If someone does not have experiences in relevant department so how they operate the system and lead the organization. Therefore it is important that extra skills have to inspire the leadership of an organization. The authority approach embraced by the chair of the detachment affects departmental accomplishment. Be that as it may, the various sorts of the office found inside an optional school likewise make the administration of a detachment an especially troublesome and complex job to satisfy (Busher and Harris, 1999).

Suitable methodology

For every organization, It is very important that If they hiring a person the organization must provide the workshops and trainings for the better job satisfaction. My respondent told me that:

“After appointment, there are many exceptions if sometime find a way to get special preparation courses in foreign countries which supports by foreign NGO’s. It is important that when we hire someone as a leader, he or she must have special skills, special leadership qualities before appointment”

Although, there are no special rules for hiring but the government taking a hiring test and after it depend on the related department that how can they providing trainings workshops and seminars. This requires the subject head to be in contact with an assortment of entertainers and wellsprings of data in the outside condition of the school and to arrange, was important, in the interest of different individuals from the department (Busher; 1992).

Information and skills

The data obtained from the respondent about relevant skills, training and information provided by trainers for appoint a head of department. He indicated that:

“Yet, it is also in poor condition and I hope it will be better in the future. Before appointment of leader we do not pay attention to the need of leadership skills and after If we have opportunity, we give them training which are very important and important for an organizational leaders. They provide us relevant and skillful information about leadership because without leadership skills, the mention department become as like roofless building.”

After appointment, the ministry of higher education has an act and after passing the special training course of three or six months, someone will be able to get a position in a leadership authority or as a leader. The balance of steadiness and adjusted improvement describes this department as a moving department (Rosenholtz, 1989).

Prospective Plan

The respondent told about the future plan about some training and skills which re not attend before or necessary that:

“I have plan to get master degree in leadership for my position and the government has to plan for every leader that who do not have the special degree or course they must attend the leadership courses and master degree”

For improving quality of preparation course, the head of department suggests that government must arrange course of three or four months within the country or abroad. The ministry of higher education stated in the strategic plan that every for every department will have special training especially for those who never attended any kind of leadership training. The balance of steadiness and adjusted improvement describes this department as a moving department (Rosenholtz, 1989).

Relevant offers

The interviewees mention that there are different types of programs that I attended and the skills I got from that as like:

“I attended lots of trainings and workshops which are related to my field of profession. I learn more from those talented lecturers and they provide practically training to us. I want and suggest to our ministry about such a kinds of training and seminars for the head of department”.

The ministry of higher education has to plan about all leaders which are working in the high position of the ministry to provide courses and special workshops within the country and abroad. However, the study on departmental suitability (see, for instance, Sammons et al, 1997) shows that detachment is differentially successful. This would recommend that detachment at various degrees of capability will require typical improvement systems.

Beneficial Leadership

The facts found from the defendant about the leadership skills which he is operating in the department as:

“When I was appointed I do not have any information about the technics, rules, regulation, solving the problem, communications to others, arranging meetings,

speech on stage etc. After I attended leadership course I will know about leadership skills, theories and did practically”.

For every leader it is important that he/she have to attend the special course of leadership and implement in their department. (Glover et al. 1998) note, it recommends a significant coaching or supervisory position of authority in supporting university advancement and the improvement of students scholastically and socially.

Become Effective leader

The ministry of Higher education stated that in the annual plan that they will provide courses and workshops for dean of faculty and for head of department. The interviewees also mention that:

“I have to plan get master degree in leadership and after that PhD on same department, that will help in improve my leadership quality and to get promotion from head of department to dean of faculty. It is more effective for me and all of head of department of Afghanistan”.

The continuation of the above mention points will help leaders to feel more powerful, more informative; can get extra skills and the capability to solve the problems on the spot. The most important is, these types of leaders will arise and will shine the name of their organizations. This growth in desires has been joined by a string of government arrangements planned for creating the force for school improvement, including formative arranging, target setting and performance of the board (Fidler, 1999).

Conclusion

This little article introduced a complete procedure for leading a proper evaluation of preparation requirements for head of department in higher education. We accept this structure will support to seal the hole in proficient advancement packages for head of department. Further, the subjective research examined right now concerns noted in past research with respect to the absence of accord in recognizing errands and duties of office seats over the college and the absence of inclusion of seats in formal administrative preparation (see Sharma, 1971). By concentrating on the imperative information, aptitudes, and capacities seats use to achieve explicit undertakings are maybe progressively generalizable across divisions in the college.

The incorporation of the examination gave numerous points of view on trainings needs from applicable constituents while guaranteeing that occupants were effectively engaged with the appraisal. In spite of the fact that chairs gave comparable appraisals of preparing need on many occasions for certain things (for example information on protected innovation rights, capacity to advance the division or program's picture and notoriety and capacity to urge employees to submit a proposition for outer agreements and awards).

Generally speaking, this item might be viewed as a experimental revision that gives a significant showing of how to lead an appraisal of preparing requirements for training needs for department. It is our expectation that this investigation will encourage activities to address the constrained preparing chances that numerous heads now knowledge in universities in Afghanistan and worldwide; endeavors ought to be made to reproduce our strategies and results in assorted societies around the globe.

Future Research and Limitations

Regardless of the usefulness of this revision methodology to recognizing preparing requirements for department chairs, it does have limitations. One potential limitation is that reactions may have been dependent upon determination predisposition; in that lone those heads who touched they were most needing training responded. If so, in any case, we would recommend that these are decisively the people whose reactions are generally significant, as people who choose not to react in light of the fact that they are happy with the norm may not give important indicative data about the preparation needs of new chairs. Further, it is possible that high scores on chair professional improvement' may likewise reflect request attributes or potential reaction inclination. Through the strategy portrayed right now, college can conceivably give an advisory group the data and strategies expected to distinguish the preparation needs of that university's department chairs. At long last, I thank an unidentified referee for bringing up which we prohibited extra vital voting public, the regulatory worker, since this research. We firmly urge upcoming research to deliberate these essential persons and job, in point of view on head of department training.

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Acknowledgements

I might want to say thanks to Dr. LOKMAN BIN MOHD TAHIR, professor of Education faculty at UTM, Johor Bahru Malaysia, for his help all through this research. I might likewise want to say thanks to Hamza Atifnigar and Ziaurahman Zaheer, department of TESEL, UTM, Johor Bahru Malaysia, for their inclusion during the underlying phases of the project.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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